

Aerobic M9 0.2% Casmino Acids

Supplementary Figure S4. Growth curves of WT (green circle), $\Delta aceE$ (dark grey square), $\Delta aceF$ (grey triangle) in M9 0.2% Casamino acid media grown aerobically. Data represent the average and SEM for three independent biological replicates.